

Tools for stakeholder consultation to inform the preparation of the CAP Strategic Plans

OBJECTIVES AND CHALLENGES

Member States are required by Reg. 2115/2021 (Art. 106) to involve a broad range of stakeholders and authorities in consultation activities. The main challenges for this task are to define which steps of the design process should be informed by consultation activities, and the **proper engagement approach** (open versus restricted, co-creative versus informative, bottom-up versus top-down, or a combination of them), while ensuring the transparency of the process. In fact, several engagement strategies are available to involve stakeholders, each with different implications. Generally speaking, the choice of engagement tools should be **adjusted to the policy design step** that is informed by the consultation.

MAIN TOOLS ADOPTED: STRENGTHS AND WEAKNESSES

Online consultation platforms (Impactons (FR) and Otakantaa.fi (FI))

Generally based on designated online platforms, online consultations are dissemination and opinion collection strategies aiming at disseminating to and gathering diverse perspectives from a vast audience. This tool can combine **social media dissemination** and **feedback monitoring** with online **questionnaires** and dedicated mailboxes to collect opinions. The consultations can be permanent all along the plans' preparation process and/or focus on specific steps of the plans' design.

It allows the involvement of a very large and diverse audience, through multiple complementary virtual channels, that is not reachable with traditional consultation methods. Considering the potential audience, it is relatively cost-effective.

The accessibility to digital technologies differs among stakeholders, possibly leading to an unbalanced audience composition, whereas bigger interest groups might self-select. Processing large amounts of qualitative information can be complex and time-demanding, and the inputs' origin is hardly traceable.

Town Hall Meetings (IR)

The tool consists of meetings that are conducted throughout the country on various dates, offering an **accessible platform for stakeholders to share their views, concerns, and suggestions** regarding CAP reforms. Additionally, these meetings can take place virtually. Initially, an informative presentation on the consultation topic is delivered, succeeded by one or **more Q&A sessions** about the topic, during which participants' feedback is gathered. Public consultation documents containing specific questions related to the topic are also distributed to participants. Their responses and feedback are then collected through additional means such as email or mail.

It enables the engagement of a large and diverse range of stakeholders throughout the whole territory, whereby different local perspectives can be captured.

The processing of the collected data can be very time-demanding, and setting up a structured approach for a meaningful analysis can be difficult.

World Café (DE, FI)

The world café method is a structured conversational process for **knowledge sharing** in which small groups of people discuss a topic at several small tables (like in a café). A world café can be made up of several thematic workshops, shedding light on different topics. The workshops start with short presentations related to the topic, which are followed by group discussions and idea collection (e.g. on whiteboard papers). Each group has a host that poses the questions/issues to be answered/debated and notes down the answers. At the end of each round, the participants (except for the hosts) are reshuffled into new groups, starting a new round of conversation. The host shares the insights from the previous groups with the new one. It ends with all hosts sharing the main takeaways for a joint discussion. This tool is usually used to **identify strengths, weaknesses, and development needs** related to different topics in a participatory and engaging way.

The tool allows the involvement of a broad range of diverse stakeholders, help cross-pollinate ideas and build upon each other's contributions, and explore complex topics from multiple perspectives in a structured way.

It requires the involvement of a large group of participants and intense facilitation to feed the discussion, whereas the output can tend to over-summarise the collected ideas.

